

Classification through Kernel Density Estimation and Random Fourier Features with Label-Based Weighting, Feature Pruning, and the Laplacian Kernel

Emilie Kjeldsberg Sivertsen

Norwegian University of Science and Technology,
Department of Computer Science,
NO-7491 Trondheim, Norway

emilieks@stud.ntnu.no

Ole Christian Eidheim

Norwegian University of Science and Technology,
Department of Computer Science,
NO-7491 Trondheim, Norway

ole.c.eidheim@ntnu.no

Abstract

Random features provide an approximation of kernel functions, enabling kernel methods to scale more effectively to large datasets. Probability densities for use in a Bayes classifier can then be constructed through kernel density estimation with reduced storage and computational requirements, resulting in a tractable and highly parallelizable classification framework. However, the use of random features in kernel density estimation can degrade the classification accuracy, and therefore a label-based weighting scheme is presented to alleviate this and at the same time improve classification performance for larger kernel widths¹. A pruning mechanism is also introduced that removes random features not essential to the density estimation with only a small impact on the classification results in some settings. Finally, the Laplacian kernel is chosen to reduce sensitivity to the kernel width parameter, and to better model less smooth probability densities.

1 Introduction

Kernel density estimation (Rosenblatt, 1956; Parzen, 1962) computes the probability density of a new data point using the weighted average density of the training set, where similar data points are typically given higher weights. The similarity is measured by a normalized kernel function $k(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$ that integrates to one, such as the normalized d -dimensional Gaussian kernel $k_{\text{Gaussian}}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \frac{1}{(\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma)^d} \exp(-\frac{\|\mathbf{u}-\mathbf{v}\|_2^2}{2\sigma^2})$ with width parameter $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ and where $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the l_2 -norm. Let $\mathbf{x}^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^d$, $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ be N training samples, the probability density is then defined as:

$$\hat{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N k(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}^{(i)})$$

Random Fourier features (Rahimi & Recht, 2007) enable certain kernel functions, that is positive definite shift-invariant, to be approximated by the dot product of the two transformed inputs:

$$k(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) \approx z(\mathbf{u}) \cdot z(\mathbf{v})$$

where $z : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^D$ or \mathbb{R}^{2D} is a randomized feature map with D random features that satisfies the condition $\mathbb{E}_{\omega \sim p(\omega)} [z_\omega(\mathbf{u}) \cdot z_\omega(\mathbf{v})] = k(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$, and $p(\omega)$ is the Fourier transform of the given kernel function. For example, using $k_{\text{Gaussian}}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$, then $p(\omega) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \frac{1}{\sigma^2} I_d)$. Of the two mappings presented in Rahimi & Recht (2007), the mapping with strictly lower-variance for Gaussian kernels and better uniform convergence bound (Sutherland & Schneider, 2015) is:

$$z(\mathbf{x}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{D}} \left(z_{\omega_1}(\mathbf{x}), \dots, z_{\omega_D}(\mathbf{x}) \right) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{D}} \left(\cos(\omega_1 \cdot \mathbf{x}), \dots, \cos(\omega_D \cdot \mathbf{x}), \sin(\omega_1 \cdot \mathbf{x}), \dots, \sin(\omega_D \cdot \mathbf{x}) \right) \quad (1)$$

where $\omega_{1:D}$ are sampled from $p(\omega)$, and in this case $z : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{2D}$. The convergence of $z(\mathbf{u}) \cdot z(\mathbf{v})$ to $k(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$ in D is exponentially fast (Rahimi & Recht, 2007).

¹The source code for the experiments in this article can be found at <https://gitlab.com/eidheim/kde-rf-classification>.

Figure 1: Difference between two kernel density estimation results of red and blue labeled data using random features. (a) With Gaussian kernel. (b) With Gaussian kernel and label-based weighting. (c) With Laplacian kernel. (d) With Laplacian kernel and label-based weighting. (e) Same as (d) but with pruned weak frequency components. (f) Same as (d) but with pruned strong frequency components. In all experiments where applicable, $N = 100$, $D = 1000$, $\sigma = \frac{1}{2}$, $\eta = 1$, and the weighting algorithm was run 10 times. Half of the components were kept in (e) and (f), and pruning was performed after label-based weighting.

Traditional kernel density estimation requires all training samples to compute a probability density, however, when combined with random features, only the mean feature vector of the training set needs to be stored (Veeramachaneni, 2010):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{f}(\mathbf{x}) &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N k(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}^{(i)}) \\
 &\approx \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N z(\mathbf{x}) \cdot z(\mathbf{x}^{(i)}) \\
 &= z(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N z(\mathbf{x}^{(i)})
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

2 Classification using Kernel Density Estimation with Random Features

For simplicity, all classes are assumed equally likely, which allows for a reduced Bayes classifier:

$$\hat{y} = \operatorname{argmax}_{c \in \{1, \dots, C\}} \tilde{f}_c(\mathbf{x})$$

where $\tilde{f}_c(\mathbf{x})$ is the estimated density, using random features, from the training data points having label c , and C is the number of distinct labels. The density functions $\tilde{f}_{1:C}(\mathbf{x})$ do not need to be normalized, but each applied kernel function that is approximated must integrate to the same scalar.

Let the mean feature vector in the density estimate (2) for label c be:

$$\mathbf{m}_c = \frac{1}{N_c} \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ y^{(i)}=c}}^N z_c(\mathbf{x}^{(i)})$$

where N_c is the number of data points having label c , $y^{(i)}$ is the label of $\mathbf{x}^{(i)}$, and $z_c(\mathbf{x})$ is the feature map with random features $\omega_{c,1:D}$ for label c . Then the density estimate for label c is:

$$\tilde{f}_c(\mathbf{x}) = z_c(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{m}_c$$

Note that using a single kernel function with the same random features for all label feature maps, i.e. $\forall c \in \{1, \dots, C\} \omega_{c,1:D} = \omega_{1:D}$ and thus $z_c(\mathbf{x}) = z(\mathbf{x})$, enables efficient caching of the dataset feature mappings.

2.1 Label-Based Weighting

Kernel density estimation is applied separately to data for each label and does not inherently account for the densities of data points from other labels. With larger kernel widths, the estimated densities may be too smooth to correctly classify points near other points with different labels. To sharpen the density estimates in these regions, a basic label-based weighting scheme is introduced in Algorithm 1. In this algorithm, misclassified data points receive higher density weights for the correct labels, while the density estimates for the incorrectly predicted labels are correspondingly reduced. See Figures 1(a) to 1(d) for example density results before and after applying the algorithm.

Algorithm 1 Label-based weighting that adjusts the mean feature vectors $\mathbf{m}_{1:C}$ based on incorrect predictions from the training data points $\mathbf{x}^{(1:N)}$ and labels $y^{(1:N)}$. The weight updates can be scaled by $\eta \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$.

incorrect \leftarrow array of size N
predictions \leftarrow array of size N

for $i \leftarrow 1$ to N **do**

\triangleright Can run in parallel

$\hat{y} \leftarrow \operatorname{argmax}_{c \in \{1, \dots, C\}} \tilde{f}_c(\mathbf{x}^{(i)})$

if $\hat{y} \neq y^{(i)}$ **then**

incorrect[i] \leftarrow *true*

predictions[i] \leftarrow \hat{y}

else

incorrect[i] \leftarrow *false*

end if

end for

for $c \leftarrow 1$ to C **do**

\triangleright Can run in parallel

for $i \leftarrow 1$ to N **do**

if *incorrect*[i] **then**

if $c = y^{(i)}$ **then**

$\mathbf{m}_c \leftarrow \mathbf{m}_c + \eta z_c(\mathbf{x}^{(i)})$

else if $c = \text{predictions}[i]$ **then**

$\mathbf{m}_c \leftarrow \mathbf{m}_c - \eta z_c(\mathbf{x}^{(i)})$

end if

end if

end for

end for

The algorithm can be run after the probability densities have been estimated for all labels, and can be repeated for any number of iterations. Even though the algorithm performs classifications of every data point in the training set, each classification requires only one dot product per distinct label if the dataset mappings are cached. Algorithm 1 was also written to be easily parallelizable.

2.2 Pruning Non-Essential Random Features

The parts of the mean feature vectors $\mathbf{m}_{1:C}$ representing weak frequency components of the probability densities may be removed without significantly affecting the density estimates. The strength of a frequency component $j \in \{1, \dots, D\}$ for label c can be quantified by the magnitude of the mean feature elements accumulated by the cosine-sine pair containing ω_j in (1):

$$\sqrt{m_{c,j}^2 + m_{c,j+D}^2}$$

where the phase information is consequently disregarded. The components with the lowest magnitude can then be removed from \mathbf{m}_c , together with every corresponding $\omega_{c,j}$, for each label. Example densities with strong and weak frequency components are shown in Figures 1(e) and 1(f), respectively.

2.3 Laplacian Kernel

Let the normalized d -dimensional Laplacian kernel be defined as

$$k_{\text{Laplacian}}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \frac{\Gamma(d/2)}{2\pi^{d/2}\sigma^d\Gamma(d)} \exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}\|_2}{\sigma}\right) \quad (3)$$

where $\Gamma(a)$ is the gamma function. The Laplacian kernel is generally less sensitive to the width parameter than the Gaussian kernel because it decays more gradually with distance. Furthermore, the Laplacian kernel has a

sharp cusp at its origin, which can be advantageous when modeling less smooth densities from the training data. To capture such densities using approximated Gaussian kernels, smaller kernel widths are required, but Rahimi & Recht (2007)’s Claim 1 shows that this would lead to a larger kernel approximation error. Figures 1(a) to 1(d) show example densities from Gaussian and Laplacian kernels using random features.

Of the two Fourier feature mappings in Rahimi & Recht (2007), (1) has strictly lower-variance for the Laplacian kernel, because the inequality from Sutherland & Schneider (2015) holds:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}k(2\Delta) - k(\Delta)^2 &\leq \frac{1}{2} \\ k(2\Delta) &\leq 2k(\Delta)^2 \\ \exp\left(-\frac{\|2(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v})\|_2}{\sigma}\right) &\leq 2 \exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}\|_2}{\sigma}\right)^2 \\ \exp\left(-\frac{2\|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}\|_2}{\sigma}\right) &\leq 2 \exp\left(-\frac{2\|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}\|_2}{\sigma}\right) \end{aligned}$$

where shift-invariant kernels depend only on the difference between the inputs, commonly denoted by $k(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = k(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}) = k(\Delta)$.

The Fourier transform of (3) is an isotropic multivariate Cauchy distribution with scale $\frac{1}{\sigma}$. We can then sample $\omega_{1:D}$ as in Roth (2012), for each $j \in \{1, \dots, D\}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{a}_j &\sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \frac{1}{\sigma^2}I_d), \\ b_j &\sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1), \\ \omega_j &\leftarrow \frac{\mathbf{a}_j}{|b_j|} \end{aligned}$$

3 Experiments

Figure 2 shows classification results on the MNIST dataset using different combinations of $D = 1000$ and 10000 random features, label-based weighting, pruning, and Gaussian and Laplacian kernels. Unless otherwise specified, the label-based weighting algorithm was run for 1000 iterations with $\eta = 1$. Results from the nearest neighbor classifier and traditional kernel density estimation with exact Gaussian and Laplacian kernels are also included in the figures.

Label-based weighting with the Laplacian kernel shows reliable high accuracy across a large range of widths in Figure 2(a), even though the Gaussian kernel has higher accuracy for some kernel widths. Traditional kernel density estimation performed better with small kernel widths. Note that we did not test label-based weighting on traditional kernel density estimation since this is intractable for very large datasets, but it is plausible that similar improvements could be seen here as well. However, we did experiment with gradient descent on $\tilde{g}_c(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{w}) = z(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \frac{1}{N_c} \left(\sum_{i=1, y^{(i)}=c}^N w_i z(\mathbf{x}^{(i)}) + \sum_{i=1, y^{(i)} \neq c}^N (1 - w_i) z(\mathbf{x}^{(i)}) \right)$ with initially $\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{1}$ and e.g. cross-entropy loss², but so far we have only observed longer training time to reach comparable test accuracy scores. Gradient descent is also highly sensitive to the choice of learning rate and number of training epochs.

The choice of η does not seem to significantly affect the performance of the label-based weighting algorithm. Of course, if η is too small, more iterations are required to achieve the same training or test accuracy, but a wide range of η values can yield similar results. This is demonstrated in Figure 2(a), where the test accuracies show little overall difference between $\eta = 1$ and $\eta = 10000$. Furthermore, a large η might help preserve the label-based adjustments across multiple training batches.

The pruning results shown in Figure 2(b), applied after label-based weighting, outperform only at lower kernel widths. At higher kernel widths, label-based weighting without pruning, but with an equally reduced number of features, achieved better accuracy.

Figure 2(c) shows classification results with different number of weighting iterations. Here it appears that larger widths require additional iterations for the results to become more stable. At lower widths, the training set accuracy may reach 1, and the weighting procedure can then stop early, as computing the training set accuracy may be done effectively during each iteration.

The accuracy on the training set for the Laplacian kernel is high as seen in Figure 2(d), particularly with many iterations. Moreover, with fewer random features and smaller kernel widths, the training accuracy can give some measure of how well the classifier will perform on the test set.

²Example code can be found at: https://gitlab.com/eidheim/kde-rf-classification/-/blob/main/gradient_descent.py.

Figure 2: Accuracy scores on the MNIST dataset with different kernels and parameters. (a) Comparison between traditional and random feature (RF) approximations of Gaussian and Laplacian kernels with and without label-based weighting. (b) Pruning results where $\frac{1}{10}$ of the strongest frequency components were kept. (c) Results from different numbers of weighting iterations. (d) Training accuracy scores.

References

- Emanuel Parzen. On estimation of a probability density function and mode. *The Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, 33(3):1065 – 1076, 1962. doi: 10.1214/aoms/1177704472. URL <https://doi.org/10.1214/aoms/1177704472>.
- Ali Rahimi and Benjamin Recht. Random features for large-scale kernel machines. In J. Platt, D. Koller, Y. Singer, and S. Roweis (eds.), *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 20. Curran Associates, Inc., 2007. URL https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2007/file/013a006f03dbc5392effeb8f18fda755-Paper.pdf.
- Murray Rosenblatt. Remarks on some nonparametric estimates of a density function. *The Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, 27(3):832 – 837, 1956. doi: 10.1214/aoms/1177728190. URL <https://doi.org/10.1214/aoms/1177728190>.
- Michael Roth. *On the Multivariate t Distribution*. Linköping University Electronic Press, 2012. URL <http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:liu:diva-91686>.
- Danica J Sutherland and Jeff Schneider. On the error of random fourier features. *arXiv*, 2015. doi: 0.48550/arXiv.1506.02785. URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1506.02785>.
- Harsha Veeramachaneni. Random fourier features for kernel density estimation, 2010. URL <https://mlstat.wordpress.com/2010/10/04/random-fourier-features-for-kernel-density-estimation/>.